

The Mercury/Mercurous Acetate Electrode : Standard Potential in Dioxan-Water Media at 25°C.

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Standard potentials of the Hg/Hg₂ (OAc)₂ electrode in dioxan-water media (containing 20, 30, 45 and 70% by weight of dioxan) have been determined at 25°C using a cell of the type.

and the values obtained on the molality scale are 0.48035, 0.45980, 0.43170 and 0.31400 abs. V. respectively.

From the E_m^0 values the standard free energy change (ΔG_0) for the cell reaction in the media were calculated to be -22.156, -21.208, -19.912 and -14.482 Kcal. respectively in water-dioxan media containing 20, 30, 45 and 70% by weight of dioxan compared to -23.584 Kcal. for the cell reaction in water. The dependance of the standard potentials on the dielectric constants of the media in the light of the Born equation as well as the volume fraction of water (ϕ_w) in the light of Feakins-French relationship has been examined.

Larson and co-workers¹⁻³ have shown that the mercury/mercurous acetate electrode functions reversibly in acetic acid solutions and have determined its standard potential at different temperatures. The potentialities of the mercury/mercurous acetate electrode as a reference electrode in acetate buffer solutions have not been fully explored. It has been used as an internal reference electrode for glass electrodes filled with Michaelis buffer (0.1 M acetic acid and 0.1 M sodium acetate) by Schwabe and Glockner⁴⁻⁵.

Covington, Talukdar and Thirsk⁶ also determined the standard potential of the mercury/mercurous acetate electrode in acetate buffer solutions containing sodium or manganous ions (511.3 mV). Below certain low acetate concentrations deviations from the expected values were found probably due to the solubility of mercurous acetate or the formation of a basic species.

So far as non-aqueous or mixed media are concerned, Schwabe⁷ first used this electrode successfully in solutions of acetic acid in methanol and isopropanol saturated with sodium or lithium acetate. A potential of 423.0 ± 0.5 mV was obtained for the electrode Hg/Hg₂ (OAc)₂(s), methanol (99%) satd. with NaOAc vs the standard H₂-electrode. For the Hg/Hg₂

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2. W. D. Larson and W. J. Tomsicek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 65.
3. W. D. Larson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 937.
4. K. Schwabe and G. Glockner, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 504.
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7. K. Schwabe, *Naturwiss.*, 1957, 44, 350.

(OAc)₂ (s), isopropanol (96%) satd. with LiOAc a potential of 453.0 ± 0.5 mV was obtained. In the present work we have determined E_m^0 values and certain thermodynamic quantities in Dioxan-water media.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mercurous acetate was precipitated by mixing approx. 0.1 (N) solution of A.R. mercurous nitrate and recrystallised sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of $pH < 4$. The precipitate was washed with acetic acid solutions (> 0.5 molar) and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. Mercury/mercurous acetate electrodes were prepared using the electrode compartment design as used by Prasad and co-workers⁸

A thin layer of mercurous acetate slurry in acetic acid was introduced on to the surface of mercury which had been distilled twice under reduced pressure. A pair of electrodes selected for use agreed within 0.1 mV.

The methods of preparation of hydrogen electrodes and the hydrogen purification train and saturators were the same as those of Beck, Singh and Wynne-Jones⁹ with slight modification. The electrode vessel had seven mouths with B-7 std. joints, two for Pt-electrode, two for hydrogen bubbling, one out-let for hydrogen gas (trap filled with the same solution), one inlet for solution and the other fitted with a tap and connected to a pair of mercury/mercurous acetate electrode through a vessel containing the same solution. This arrangement permits the comparison of two mercury/mercurous acetate electrodes with two hydrogen electrodes. The asymmetry between two hydrogen electrodes or between two mercury/mercurous acetate electrodes could also be checked. The maximum asymmetry between two hydrogen electrodes allowed was 0.05 mV. Before use the mercury/mercurous acetate electrodes were flushed 5 times with the experimental solution and then allowed to stand overnight in this solution before the cell was assembled and placed in the air-thermostat at $25.0 (\pm 0.05)^\circ\text{C}$.

Dilute A.R. acetate acid was standardized by standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution.

For the calculation of molality of the solution the density of the solution was determined. As the weight percent of dioxan increases, the dielectric constant falls rapidly and accurate measurement of e.m.f. becomes difficult because of the increase in internal resistance of the cell. For 70% dioxan media, acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer was used.

B.D.H. (Analar) dioxan was refluxed for 48 hours with NaOH, distilled, treated with metallic sodium to remove traces of water and peroxides, and stored over sodium metal. Freshly distilled solvent and double distilled water were used in the work.

E.m.f. measurements were made by using a Leeds—Northrup K₂ type potentiometer and L.N. galvanometer enabling the e.m.f. to be read directly to 0.05 mV. Cells reached equilibrium in two hours. The tap connecting the H₂-electrode to the mercury/mercurous acetate electrode was opened only while measurements were being made. The e.m.f. readings

8. S. Nath, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 28, 683.

9. W. H. Beck, K. P. Singh and W. F. K. Wynne-Jones, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, 55, 331

were corrected to 1 atm. pressure of hydrogen. We have got the vapour pressures of the dioxan-water media from the determinations by Hovorka, Schaefer and Dreisbach¹⁰

Theory : For the cell

where OAc = acetate, the cell reaction is

The e.m.f. of the cell is

$$E = E_m^0 - \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{H}^+} m_{\text{OAc}^-} \gamma_{\text{OAc}^-} \quad \dots (1)$$

where γ with appropriate subscripts represents the activity coefficients.

For first three mixed media ($m_2 = 0$), considering the dissociation of acetic acid

where α is called the degree of dissociation.

We have $m_{\text{H}^+} = m_{\text{OAc}^-} = m_1\alpha$ and introducing the concept of mean ionic activity instead of individual ionic activity eq. (1) becomes to

$$\begin{aligned} E &= E_m^0 - \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_1^2 \alpha^2 \gamma_{\pm}^2 \\ &= E_m^0 - 2k \log m_1 \alpha \gamma_{\pm} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (2)$$

where

$$k = 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F}$$

The degree of dissociation (α) and mean ionic activity coefficients (γ_{\pm}) have been calculated by successive approximation from the dissociation constant expression

$$K = \frac{m_1^2 \alpha^2 \gamma_{\pm}^2}{m_1(1-\alpha)\gamma_u} \quad \dots (3)$$

and the Debye-Huckel limiting equation

$$\log \gamma_{\pm} = -\frac{Az_+z_-\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1+B\alpha\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (4)$$

where γ_u is the activity coefficient of unionised acetic acid molecules and considered as unity for our calculation. $\mu =$ ionic strength $= m_1\alpha$ for the present case. $a =$ ion size parameter of acetate ion which was taken as 4.5 \AA , the same as in aqueous media. A and B are the Debye-Huckel constants and were calculated in the molal scale by the usual method using the exact values of the density, dielectric constant etc. of the mixed aquo-organic solvent.

The values of E_m^0 were determined for every molality from eq (2) using equations (3) and (4). These values, as expected, were not constant and have been tabulated as $E_m^{0'}$. The plot of $E_m^{0'}$ against μ extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave the correct standard potential for the electrode in that media.

For 70% dioxan media, in which acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer (where $m_2 \neq 0$) has been used, the cell e.m.f. relation becomes

$$\begin{aligned} E &= E_m^0 - k \log K - k \log m_u \gamma_u \\ &= E_m^0 - k \log K - k \log (m_1 - m') \gamma_u \end{aligned} \quad \dots (5)$$

$m_u =$ molality of undissociated acid molecule and m' is given sufficiently accurately by $K \frac{m_1}{m_2}$ in this case.

For the buffer solutions the effect of the salt upon the activity coefficient of acetic acid can be represented by¹¹.

$$\log \gamma_u = S \cdot \mu \quad \dots (6)$$

where S is known as salting coefficient. Thus, defining

$$E^{0'} \equiv E + k \log K + k \log (m_1 - m') \quad \dots (7)$$

We have,

$$E^{0'} = E_m^0 - k \cdot S \cdot \mu \quad \dots (8)$$

where E_m^0 was obtained by the extrapolation of the linear plot of $E^{0'}$ against μ .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables I-III give the necessary data for determination of E_m^0 and its values ($E_m^{0'}$) calculated from the equation (2). The last column gives the E_m^0 value at zero ionic strength. Table IV is for 70% dioxan media. Ionic strength in this media is practically equal to molality of sodium acetate.

11. F. A. Long and W. F. McDevit, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, 51, 119.

TABLE I

Temp. = 25.0°C.

Weight percent of Dioxan (W) = 20.

m_1	$\mu \times 10^3$	E.m.f. of the cell at 1 atm. press in abs. V.	$2k \log m_1 \alpha \gamma_{\pm}$	E°_m	E°_m
1.7986	3.3174	0.78398	-0.29794	0.48604	
1.6154	3.1364	0.78563	-0.30074	0.48489	
1.5486	3.0683	0.78578	-0.30182	0.48396	
1.4030	2.9140	0.78693	-0.30436	0.48257	
1.2625	2.7582	0.78943	-0.30708	0.48235	0.48035
1.1394	2.6149	0.79283	-0.30854	0.48429	
0.99212	2.4334	0.79738	-0.31327	0.48411	
0.84970	2.2453	0.80108	-0.31726	0.48382	
0.70946	2.0448	0.80518	-0.32190	0.48328	
0.56755	1.8217	0.81018	-0.32764	0.48254	

TABLE II

Weight percent of Dioxan (W) = 30

m_1	$\mu \times 10^3$	E.m.f. of the cell at 1 atm. press in abs. V.	$2k \log m_1 \alpha \gamma_{\pm}$	E°_m	E°_m
1.9036	2.2874	0.78428	-0.31732	0.46696	
1.7201	2.1692	0.78713	-0.31993	0.46720	
1.5072	2.0247	0.79008	-0.32332	0.46676	
1.2929	1.8690	0.79368	-0.32726	0.46642	
1.0790	1.7009	0.79738	-0.33192	0.46546	0.45980
0.96720	1.6068	0.79978	-0.33473	0.46505	
0.86352	1.5148	0.80288	-0.33764	0.46524	
0.75663	1.4144	0.80663	-0.34104	0.46559	
0.64869	1.3058	0.81023	-0.34500	0.46523	
0.54050	1.1881	0.81353	-0.34969	0.46384	

The dissociation constant (K), density (d_0) and dielectric constant (D) of dioxan-water media at 25° were taken from Harned and co-workers¹². The lower limit of acetic acid concentration were kept at 0.5 M as suggested by Larson and coworkers². The expected error in the E°_m values are ± 0.1 mV.

12. H. S. Harned and J. O. Morrison, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1908.
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 H. S. Harned and L. D. Fallon, *ibid.*, 1939, 61, 2377. Revised by
 H. S. Harned, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, 43, 275.

TABLE III

Weight percent of Dioxan (W) = 45

m_1	$\mu \times 10^3$	E.m.f. of the cell at 1 atm. press in abs. V	$2k \log m_1 \alpha \gamma_{\pm}$	$E^{0'}_m$	E^0_m
1.33270	0.89315	0.79754	-0.36572	0.43182	
1.22670	0.85518	0.79924	-0.36786	0.43138	
1.12070	0.81582	0.80149	-0.37018	0.43131	
1.01490	0.77464	0.80289	-0.37272	0.43017	
0.98799	0.76379	0.80484	-0.37342	0.43142	
0.91067	0.73192	0.80659	-0.37551	0.43108	0.43170
0.82627	0.69572	0.80934	-0.37801	0.43133	
0.74226	0.65796	0.81189	-0.38076	0.43113	
0.65637	0.61709	0.81539	-0.38393	0.43146	
0.57308	0.57508	0.81854	-0.38741	0.43113	

TABLE IV

Weight percent of Dioxan (W) = 70

m_1	m_2	$\mu \times 10^3$	E.m.f. of the cell at 1 atm. in abs. V.	$E^{0'}$	E^0_m
0.64731	0.03222	32.22	0.82483	0.32148	
0.66312	0.02766	27.66	0.82303	0.32030	
0.67512	0.02421	24.21	0.82198	0.31971	
0.68792	0.02628	26.28	0.82303	0.32048	
0.68858	0.02213	22.13	0.82133	0.31881	
0.68708	0.02075	20.75	0.82058	0.31876	0.31400
0.69182	0.01938	19.38	0.82098	0.31934	
0.69661	0.01799	17.99	0.81943	0.31796	
0.70141	0.01661	16.61	0.82048	0.31919	
0.71099	0.01384	13.84	0.81818	0.31724	

The standard free energy change (ΔG_0) for the cell reaction at 25° in dioxan-water media has been calculated from the thermodynamic relation

$$\Delta G_0 = -nFE^0 \quad \dots (9)$$

where the symbols bear their usual meaning. Table V shows these values. For E^0_m in water medium a value of 0.51130 V⁶ was taken.

TABLE V

Standard potential of Mercury/mercurous acetate electrode in Dioxan water media

Wt. % of Dioxan	E_m^0 in abs. V	ΔG_0 kcal
0	0.51130	-23.584
20	0.48035	-22.156
30	0.45980	-21.208
45	0.43170	-19.912
70	0.31400	-14.482

Fig. 1 shows the variation of E_m^0 with $1/D$. The well known Born equation suggests that plots of E^0 against reciprocals of dielectric constants should be linear. But it is seen that the plot of E_m^0 against $1/D$ shows sharp deviations from the Born line when water percentages are low. The deviation from Born equation is observed at about 40% dioxan media. Ojwa¹³, and Das and co-workers¹⁴ also made similar observations for the Ag-AgCl electrode in methanol-water mixtures and Ag-AgBr electrode in ethylene glycol-water mixtures respectively. The departure from theoretical Born plots may be attributed in part to the uncertainty in the radius of the solvated ion complexes, especially in the water-poor solvents, which if different in different solvents, invalidates the very basis of the well-known linear relationship. Besides, it is well known¹⁵ that the Born equation only takes care of the so-called secondary solvation energy. Even if the solvated ion species happens to be the same in the different aqueous organic media, the primary solvation energy may not

FIG 1 PLOT OF E_m^0 AGAINST $1/D$

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necessarily remain constant. Differences in E^0 values may not, therefore, be rightly equated to the Born free energy change.

Feakins and French¹⁶ also noted the invalidity of Born's equation and, from a detailed analysis of the solvation processes suggested that ${}^sE_c^0$ on a molar scale should be linearly related to the logarithm of the volume fraction (ϕ_w) of water. Standard potentials on the molar scale were calculated from that on the molal scale by the relationship

$$E_c^0 = E_m^0 + 2k \log d_0 \quad (10)$$

where d_0 is the density of the solvent at the particular temperature. Figure 2 shows the plot of ${}^sE_c^0$ of Hg/Hg₂(OAc)₂ electrode in these media against $\log \phi_w$. It can be seen, however, that no such deviations from the predicted linear plot occur in this. This type of linear relationship has been reported for the Ag-AgCl and Ag-AgBr electrodes in ethylene glycol media¹⁴. The solvation numbers of acetic acid in these media have been calculated from the equation¹⁶

$${}^sE_m^0 = {}^wE_m^0 + nk \log w \quad \dots (11)$$

where s and w indicates mixed solvent and water media respectively. n is the solvation number. w is the weight fraction of water. The values determined are 5.4, 5.6, 5.2 and 6.4 in order of increasing weight percent of dioxan. The real proof of the validity of Feakins and French relationship, however, needs accumulation of similar experimental data with various types of electrodes in different non-aqueous and mixed media.

FIG. 2. PLOT OF E_c^0 AGAINST $\log \phi_w$.

We thank Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India, for their financial assistance.

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Received August 25, 1970